

Developing a carbon negative gas turbine based on chemical looping combustion

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Abstract— Carbon Capture and Storage is a technology of paramount importance for Sustainable Development Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Climate Action). The European Union is moving rapidly towards low carbon technologies, see the Energy Union Strategy. Coupling biofuels and carbon capture and storage to decarbonize the power and the industrial sector can be done through the development of BECCS (Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage). However there are some technical barriers to the development of this technology. If a Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) plant has to be coupled with a gas turbine, it has to work in pressurized conditions. The effect of pressure on chemical reactions and fluidized bed hydrodynamics, at the moment, is not clear. The paper presents Aspen modeling of energy integration to achieve sufficiently high electrical efficiency. Data are both taken from previous work of the research group at Instituto de Carboquímica, Zaragoza Spain and current experimental campaigns running on pressurised micro reactors and batch fluidised beds. The case is implemented in Aspen based on the “Solids” template: “Solids with metric units”. Firstly is defined the air reactor in which two materials are used: iron and air. The air reactor is connected to a cyclone and the same is for the fuel reactor. The two modules are interconnected to form a single combustor. The exit of the air reactor is linked to the gas turbine and the hot air expanding in the gas turbine is reused to heat up water to be used to produce steam for a steam turbine. Different cases are evaluated with hydrogen combustor or oxyfuel combustion process to increase turbine inlet temperature. Also different pressures are evaluated to increase the final efficiency of the plant. Accurate considerations are also done on the final costs of the plants configurations comparing coupled air and fuel reactor with the possibility to integrate them in a sole reactor following recent development on PFIR reactor and ICR reactors developed respectively by Canmet Canada and NTNU.

Keywords— Carbon Negative Technologies, Gas Turbines, Pressurised Chemical Looping Combustor, Biofuels, BECCS